

ISic1634

I.Sicily inscription 1634

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.01.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance

Catacomb Treppiedi A

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645085

Bibliography

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